

Divergent Retrato of Identical Concepts from Tamil Poems and English Sonnets

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Abstract

Tamil poems in Sangam Literature and Sonnets in English literature seem to complement each other. When comparing two or more literature, it helps to bring light of the merits of those literatures. While comparing both of them express their inner (subjective) emotions. Poems and sonnets express the identical emotional and concepts through different images and metaphors. To accomplish the aim of the paper, Tamil poems and English sonnets are chosen for comparison.

Keywords: Tamil poems, Shakespearean sonnets Emotions and concepts, comparison

Love is an emotion that is commemorated by both a common man as well as a royal king. Love is considered to be one of the most significant human feelings and the most common theme in literature. Poem expresses human feelings and emotions through images, themes, rhythms and other linguistic cues. Poets compare love with colossal images. Whereas in Tamil, sangam literature celebrates the love between thalaivan and thalavi. Sonnet plays a vital role in celebrating the love between a man and a woman.

A Sonnet is written in fourteen decasyllabic lines expressing an idea or emotion. Sonnets as a form has its origin in Italy in the latter half of the 13th century and was chiefly associated with the Italian poet Petrarch. Later, sonnet was introduced in England by Sir Thomas Wyatt and Earl of Surrey in the 1st half of the century with a variation in its form that sonnet didn't merely follow the rhyme scheme of the Italian sonnet but with Surrey's introduction of the rhyme- scheme of 3 quatrains followed by a rhyming couplet, the pattern which Shakespeare himself followed in his sonnets. Thus, the rhyme scheme of the Shakespearean sonnet is abab bcbe ,cdcd, efef, gg where the subject matter is linked through the quatrains stand apart.

Many poets express their personal feelings of love by using sonnets towards some imagined mistress which 'accounts for the artificiality of most of the Elizabethan sonnets' (Dasgupta 28) Sir Philip Sidney composed 108 sonnets titled *Astrophel and Stella* celebrating "his fruitless love for Penelope Deveneux, the daughter of his patron, the Earl of Essex" (Dasgupta 32). Spenser's Sidney's sonnets also express his heart felt love experience.

Spenser's Amoretti stands for its genuine feelings to Elizabeth Boyle, to whom his collection of 84 sonnets and dedicated them their loved ones, Shakespeare wrote for friendship and for love in 154 sonnets. 1- 126 celebrate the theme of friendship and re addressed to young man while 127-152 are addressed to the Dark Lady, the poet's mistress and celebrate the disloyalty to her who fails in love with a friend of the poet. Thus, it is evident that sonnets used as a form to express personal feelings and emotions.

Sangam poems are divided into distinct categories: Akam(interior/inner field) and puram (exterior/outer field) where the former deals with personal human feelings such as love and intimate relationship between a man and a woman and the latter deals with other phases of human experiences such as war, courage, social life and heroism.

From this contextual background it is apparent that both poems and sonnets deal with love as one common theme. Shakespeare's Sonnet and poems in Ethuthogai can be compared in the view of the divergent depictions of love as an identical theme through persona imagery, tone and brevity.

Persona is one of the elements through which writer himself. In poems, there are many personas which includes: thalaivan, thalaivai, thozhi, sevili are giving their statements about the love between thalaivan and thalaivi. Poems are written by different writers using the same personas to express the intimacy between thalaivan and thalaivi. Shakespeare has used himself to be the only persona to express the love between him and the Darklady. in the Dark lady sonnets, only Shakespeare's views are known to the readers.

Shakespeare by voicing for both Dark lady and his supposed friend will has not given the space for them to express their emotions, whereas in poems, the writers have given space to each persona to express their concern for each other.

Imagery is one of the inevitable literary devices that poets use in their poems to express their thoughts. Both in Tamil poem and in English sonnets, imageries help in expressing the physical beauty of the heroines. In Ainkurunuri 185, thalaivan says his beloved's teeth are like the shining pearls from the ford of Korkai, her mouth is like the red coral and her speech is like the sounding of the strings in the harp. Like wise in Shakespeare's sonnet 130 describe Dark lady's physical beauty using imageries but with a difference in perception of celebrating the beautification of women. He says his mistress's eyes are not like the bright Sun; her lips are not as coral as and her voice does not sound as pleasant as music, through the lines;

*"My mistress' eyes are nothing like the Sun;
Coral is far more red than her lips' red....
...I love to hear her speak, yet well I know
that music hath a far more pleasing sounds"* (sonnet 130)

His comparison reveals that his lady love does not be beautiful. In Tamil poems, ideal imageries are used to elevate the physical beauty of thalaivi.

Beyond adding rhythmic structures, poets set different shades of tones to express the nuances of their emotions supplementing to the meaning of the poem. At the level of comprehension, tone of a poem, both the Dark lady sonnets and Tamil poems exhibit a tone of yearning for love predominantly. Since the poet is the persona in the Shakespearean sonnets, the readers could feel only his tone in the sonnets.

A sonnet is composed of 14 lines where Brevity becomes necessary. Shakespeare contributed ample number of words to the English language through his sonnets. In sonnet 130, throughout the three quatrains, the poet conveys that his lady love does not fit to describe the physical beauty of a woman.

Brevity in Tamil literature is a well-established concept with Tirukkural standing as an epitome considering the significance of the number of lines in each of the sub-divisions in Ettuthogai,

brevity becomes the innate quality of Akam poems too. Hence brevity, both in Akam poems and sonnets successfully articulates the subleness of the poets' conceits.

Both Tamil poems and Shakespearean sonnets stand as epitomes of poetry in their respective literatures. The comparison between these two series of poems based on their persona, imagery, tone and brevity facilitated to both of them. In Akam poems, ideal imageries are used to describe the physical beauty of thalaivi which is a part of the celebration of womanhood. Shakespeare on the other hand, chooses to break all those typical imageries and establishes a new way of description by celebrating the reality of his lady love. Further, tone and brevity enhances the expression of holistic emotions in the Akam poems and Dark lady sonnets of Shakespeare.

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